

Recommendations in Product Personalization: An extended Example of Pipelined Filter Combination

Volker Renneberg und Uwe M. Borghoff

Author contacts:

Dipl.-Inform Volker Renneberg, Research Assistant
Fakultät für Informatik, Institut für Softwaretechnologie
Universität der Bundeswehr, München
Werner-Heisenberg-Weg 39
85577 Neubiberg, Germany
+49 89 6004 2253
volker.renneberg@unibw-muenchen.de
<http://ist.unibw-muenchen.de/People/renneberg/>

Prof. Dr. Uwe M. Borghoff, Professor
Fakultät für Informatik, Institut für Softwaretechnologie
Universität der Bundeswehr, München
Werner-Heisenberg-Weg 39
85577 Neubiberg, Germany
+49 89 6004 2274
uwe.borghoff@unibw-muenchen.de
<http://ist.unibw-muenchen.de/People/borghoff/>

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Abstract: Traditionally, customers spend most of their money for pre-configured “off-the-shelf” products. Simple product variations are offered, fine-tuning by the customer before the purchase is generally not intended. Why pay for functionality that is not wanted? Why spend money for products that are so rigid and do not satisfy a hundred percent? To remedy these issues, we discuss a possible solution based on recommendations. In our approach, traditional filtering techniques known from recommender systems guide the customer through a sophisticated product personalization process using pipelined filter combination. This process distinguishes between expert customers and novices. An extended example proves the rich capabilities of the proposed solution.

1 Introduction

Today the traditional customer-business relation builds on the fact that customers mostly spend money for pre-configured, i.e., fixed products. These “off-the-shelf” products do not allow for sophisticated individual wishes as far as the functionality or the look and feel are concerned. It becomes even worse, when a customer is not going with the mainstream business. On the good side, depending on the product and the

company's objective, variations of one product class (such as bikes, radio receivers, disk recorders, etc.) might be offered. The customer has a certain choice. However, the variations to choose from are still fixed in their characteristics and do not allow for a fine-tuning by the customer before the purchase. As an example for adaptations after the purchase, consider firmware updates or software changes that enable/disable functionality already included in the hardware. But again, the customer pays for the whole product as it is. Not to mention that the customer is obliged to adapt to the product afterwards.

All these issues are a big discomfort to customers. Why does s/he need to buy undesirable functionality or product parts – and even pay for it? Interoperability and marketing questions play a big role on the economical side, but they are out of scope and will not be discussed in this paper. So, what is the long-term goal? The customer needs a configuration system that empowers him to buy arbitrary tailored, individual products. These products will be unique in their functionality and characteristics in that they fulfil the wishes, environmental conditions and other characteristics of the customer.

Currently, the automotive industry is a precursor in these fields. By offering configuration systems to the customers in order to tailor their cars, they seem to provide a solution to the above claims. Unfortunately, those configurators have some drawbacks. Firstly, every configurator is fixed to a specific type of car, i.e., the structural knowledge is integrated into the implementation of the configuration system. This also implies that other products than cars are not supported by those systems. For more details see Leckner *et al.* (2003). Secondly, the product parts that can be configured are still predetermined by a product designer. Thus, only choices from alternatives are provided. This is not the full-fledged customization that we want. What is still missing, is a linear value range for customer-specific attributes, as discussed by Leckner and Lacher (2003). Finally, configuration support through recommendations is not included.

There is a trade-off to be considered between simple off-the-shelf product offers and (in the best of all worlds, with the help of a recommender system) full-fledged customized products. Obviously, many products have a rather complex structure with wide value ranges of their configurable attributes. Forcing the customer to configure all attributes would be an unbearable task with regard to time and skills. Imagine you want to buy a television set, and a virtual configuration system guides you through a several hour lasting product adaptation phase. Furthermore, for being able to configure her/his product, the customer has to have a good technical expertise in the fields of the desired product. Provided customers will be allowed to virtually configure all their products, they all have to have equally deep insight knowledge into all products. Obviously the products' complexity will make configurator without recommendations system unusable. Here recommendations can be thought of as personalized products (or as we will see further down: restricted product variety). Recommendations can be used in different contexts. On the one hand, recommender systems can support a customer looking for a specific product. On the other hand, recommender systems can offer tailored advertisements with an already personalized product. I.e., after starting a product configurator, a first recommendation is already provided as a first shot of the desired (end-)product to the customer. S/he will be able to alternate some attributes and further configure the product. However, since most of the product has been configured already, no deep technical expertise is needed any longer. The degree of recommendations can vary: expert customers will get less, novices can get fully configured products.

This paper focuses on the generation of recommendations. It extends the work by Renneberg and Borghoff (2003). Section 2 introduces the basic recommendation model while Section 3 discusses our solution for generating recommendations. In Section 4, we present an extended example of our approach. Section 5 closes with a conclusion and a brief discussion of future research directions.

1.1 Product Model

So far, we have informally used the terms attributes, products, or value ranges etc. In the following, we will give a more precise definition of the involved data structures when describing products and their variations. Here we follow the explanations given by Leckner and Lacher 2003 as well as by Stegmann *et al.* (2003). In order to make the paper self-contained, we restate the basics.

Figure 1: Simplified Product Meta Model

We use a three-tiered architecture. (1) The *product configuration* is used to describe a fully configured product. Here every degree of freedom has been set to a specific value. This information may be used in different ways. One is to build the desired product. (2) The structure and the degrees of freedom of a specific product are described by the *product model*. It also provides information on dependencies between different configurable entities of the product. For instance, if a customer selects a NTSC television set, it does not make sense to integrate a PAL video player without conversion to the other system. We call those dependencies *constraints* in the following. (3) The *product meta model* specifies the structure of any product model. As shown in Figure 1 every product model has a hierarchical tree-like structure. Every *component* corresponds to some part of the real product. Each component can be divided into several sub-components that relate to smaller building blocks. There is one root-component, which actually stands for the whole product. To describe a whole range of products modelled by the product model, *degrees of freedom* are introduced. These are *attributes*, *optional components* and *alternatives for a component*. First, every component may contain attributes. Their value can be specified by an enumeration or a value range (or some other controlled vocabulary). In addition, components can be optional or have alternatives. To let the product model support our recommendation system, we decided to add default values for every degree of freedom to the product model. The product meta model also provides the structure of the constraints, i.e., the language in which the constraints have to be formulated.

Finally, we speak of a *restricted product model* because every product model belongs to a specific product and may just be changed by the product designer. Therefore, during the usage and purchase process such a product model is unchangeable. Unfortunately the recommender system will not always be able to create a single product recommendation (i.e., a product configuration). In many cases there are still some de-

degrees of freedom. The term *restricted product model* covers those recommendation results. Technically speaking, a restricted product model obeys the product meta model structure and just represents a narrowed version of the original product model describing a smaller spectrum of possible products. However, it is worthwhile to note that constraints cannot be changed for the restricted product model.

1.2 Configuration System

The whole configuration system consists of several building blocks. The (1) *configurator* is the mediator between the technical part of the system and the customer. It realizes the GUI and provides the interaction facilities. The configurator communicates with the (2) *product server*, the (3) *customer profile server* and the (4) *filtering manager*. The product server is responsible for mining all product models and product configurations. They are accessible via certain keys. Available information about the customer is kept organized through the customer profile server. Basically, this information is kept with attribute-value pairs. In order to organize the information space, the attributes may be grouped and structured hierarchically. Each attribute value has to be of a specific type, which ranges from String or Integer over Sets and Lists to XML. Thus it is possible to mine complex information about the customer. Koch (2002), Koch and Schubert (2003), and Koch and Möslein (2003) give a more detailed view on customer profiles. The filtering manager is the personalization component. It is responsible for generating recommendations. For a more detailed introduction into the whole configuration system consult Leckner *et al.* (2003).

2 Recommendations

After the general introduction in Section 1, we will go into more detail of recommendations now. By now it should be clear, why we need recommendations in a generic product configuration system. With the technical background introduced so far, we will state our goals in a more detailed form now. (1) We want to make use of the complete customer profile in order to allow recommendations. (2) Recommendations are used to drastically reduce the number of attributes to be configured manually. (3) We want to keep both the product configuration and the restricted product model valid during the whole interactive configuration process. This will be achieved by making use of the constraints that are part of the product model. By always keeping the configuration valid, the customer will not have to end up with an un-producible configuration.

By integrating a recommendation generator, we try to reach all of our goals. Obviously, the automatic generation of customer-tailored products is not an easy task. First of all, customer profile information has to be used. There has to be a filtering algorithm selecting the correct information located in the customer profile or other data storages like community servers or ranking and evaluation systems and transforming it into feasible restrictions to the original product model. They have to be feasible in that they have to match the customer's wishes, demands, and requirements for the new product. These wishes may touch different characteristics of the product, e.g., the technical specification needed or the functionality provided. Moreover, opinions of friends have to be paid attention to. Not to mention environmental restrictions that have to be fulfilled by the recommender system. Thus a wide range of information about the customer has to be respected to allow the system generate customer-optimal recommendations. If the sys-

tem fails to accomplish this task, customers will leave with high frustration pretty fast. In any case, recommendations are business-critical.

2.1 Current Approaches

During the last years, there has been intensive research in adjusting data according to the customers needs. Currently there are some standard techniques, which we want to present first.

2.1.1 Content-based Filtering

In the field of data recommendation (e.g., web sites or documents), the customer profile contains specific catchwords, which have to be present in the object to be forwarded to the customer. Therefore, the mere content is used to carry out the personalization procedure. In the fields of product personalization the customer profile may contain value ranges or exact values to specific attributes of the product model. Though this is a specialized way of mining personalization information, it is one technique to build customer-specific products. Meteren and Someren (2000) are a good source for content-based filtering.

2.1.2 Rule-based Filtering

This type of filtering method uses rules to transform the content of the customer profile into adjustments of the product model to the customer. For example, there may be a rule to increase the font size of a small label whenever a customer has reached a certain age provided the fact that older people often have vision problems. There may also be rules formulating additional dependencies in the product model though only valid for a specific customer. Thus, you can compare those rules with the constraints of the product model. In the context of rule-based filtering you may also think of constraints for further restrictions based on the customer profile. These can be formulated globally, or be defined for each constraint set individually.

2.1.3 Collaborative Filtering

Yet another well-known way of personalizing content is to make use of communities and friends related to the customer buying a product. Either the customers form such communities manually, or the computer calculates these communities of relating customers through algorithms we will not discuss in this paper. On the basis of such communities, the system tries to identify products that may be mutually interesting for the customers in question. For example, customer A relates to customer B. Customer A likes a product P. In case customer B wants a recommendation, the system may suggest the same product P to customer B. Of course, the relation between A and B somehow has to be connected to the content of product P. In our case this means products of related customers can be used to create new recommendations for one of those customers. Resnick and Varian (1997) as well as Sarwar *et al.* (2001) give a more extensive introduction to recommender systems and collaborative filtering in personalization. The interested reader may also find more relevant links in the communities' literature.

2.2 Discussion

2.2.1 Isolated Approaches

To sum up, (1) there are several filtering techniques for personalization using different customer profiles. Applying only one filtering technique of course utilizes those information blocks, which are reasonable for that technique. Unfortunately, other important information is left disregarded. Since product models are very complex and customers have to be supported in the best possible way, we cannot omit information that may further reduce the customer's workload in configuring the product. Additionally, every technique has problems under some circumstances, e.g., there is the cold start problem for collaborative filters. To compensate for the problems of the individual filtering techniques, we simply involve all of them in our process. (2) Every filtering algorithm has its own idiosyncrasy and has already received a certain research effort with important improvements. It does not make sense to reinvent the wheel by building a filtering module from scratch covering all known algorithms. (3) For every product, it is imaginable to provide the system with a wide range of specific filters. Therefore, concentrating on just one filter does not make sense.

2.2.2 Hybrid Approaches

We want a configurable combination of current and future filtering techniques. Such a combination is called a *hybrid*. Unfortunately, all hybrids found in the literature do not fully fulfil our requirements. Firstly, some hybrids have an internal structure that is static in the sense that the filter combination is unchangeable. So both the employed filters and their arrangement are pre-set by the given approach. Since every product has a different impact on the customer and because for every customer the configuration system is equipped with a different set of personal information (thus making certain filters for certain customers useless), a static solution is not tolerable when exploring a re-configurable combination of filters. In Section 3 we give a thorough discussion on that part of our approach. Secondly, some hybrids face another issue. Mostly they do not allow building *new* items/objects for recommendations, only *existing* items/objects get recommended (or not) to the customer—potentially including a rating. Unfortunately that approach is totally useless to us. We want to recommend new products. Every component of the product has to be tailored to the customer's needs, and due to the complex structure most of the products are unique (by the way, this is also a requirement for the whole configuration system!). Clearly, we cannot just recommend products already been sold. Balabanović and Shoham (1997), Soboroff and Nicholas (2002), Basu *et al.* (1998), and Schein *et al.* (2002) present current research approaches in building filtering hybrids.

3 Pipelined Filter Combination

Our approach aims to provide a generic combination method of filters. In the future this approach may not only be applied to product personalization, but also to every virtual system providing unique customer-tailored recommendations consisting of several building blocks (like our product model). We set up a sequence of filters, called *pipeline*. The arrangement of the filters inside the pipeline is freely configurable. Every filter in the pipeline will configure only parts of the final recommendation, in our case the restricted product model. Figure 2 gives a sketch of the pipeline.

Figure 2: Filtering Manager with Pipeline

The pipeline itself is one single component of the whole configuration system. It belongs to the so-called filtering manager, as introduced in Section 1.2. The filtering manager is responsible for the obviously necessary configuration process within the pipeline. Once the configuration system requests a recommendation (the trigger event is out of scope here), the filtering manager will be started. It creates the pipeline configuration. Then the pipeline is set up like the one sketched in the Figure 2. Here Filter A, B, and C are lined up in a sequence. In this case, the Filter A does some collaborative filtering, Filter B is content-based, whereas Filter C may just be some product specialized filter. The pipeline is passed a (restricted) product model, which will be piped through the filter sequence. During this process, the restricted product model will repeatedly be further restricted and enhanced by explanations on why certain values or ranges have been set respectively narrowed. The result of the last filter (Filter C) will be returned to the component requesting the recommendation.

It is clear by now that many characteristics of the pipeline have to be configured. The following section will list and illustrate the parameters. Also reasons will be given why each parameter is necessary. Afterwards we will shortly present why the pipeline solves our problems, and how it gets integrated into the configuration system. The following example will also concentrate on possible solutions to the problem of how to create the pipeline configuration.

3.1 Pipeline Configuration

The pipeline is configured through seven different parameters.

3.1.1 Customer requesting a Recommendation

This information is needed as a key to the customer profile.

3.1.2 (Restricted) Initial Product Model

The product model or at least a product that can be restricted to the customers needs is necessary. Still the question why we chose a product model has to be answered. Since the introduced pipeline architecture profits from different filters, these filters actu-

ally have to be technical plug-able. So the idea is that the output of filter A is the input of filter B without any further processing involved. Our first guess, to take a product configuration, does not really make sense as a product configuration represents a real product with every degree of freedom from the product model assigned. Thus, the first filter of the pipeline had been forced to create the whole product leaving no room for any further personalization. On top of that personalizing an attribute of a product does not only mean to set a specific value but also to restrict the space of possible values. Allowing a set of product configurations would solve that problem. But giving this, another thought led us to the conclusion to use a product model. It is powerful enough to only narrow the possible space of a degree of freedom (for all attributes, optional components, and alternatives), and it also allows restricting a degree of freedom to an exactly one value wide field. A third solution is to handle sets of product models. Think of a setting where one filter creates two totally different recommendations, e.g., a sportive car set up and a conservative limousine. Presenting both using one product model may confuse the customer. Still as a first approach we did not choose the multiple product model solution. Future research will show whether this has to be changed.

Due to the modular structure of the pipeline and the interactive design of the configuration system one input to the pipeline has to be a (restricted) product model. In case the customer restarts the pipeline with an altered version of an already restricted product model, this filtering run would not get the original product model but the already restricted one.

3.1.3 Used Filters

This issue is closely connected with the next pipeline parameter. Assume two different customers looking for a television set. Customer A is a professional and member of a big community of interest. Customer B just wants to have something useful without fancy functionality. Thus, Customer B may not even have a lot of friends the collaborative filter could use in order to assemble a recommendation from their products. This argumentation does not hold for Customer A as her/his case is completely different. Here the collaborative filter has a wide information base enabling it to use other products. In case these customers have ranked and evaluated their products, it is even possible to take this information into account. So it is easy to see that different customers demand different filters to be used in the recommendation process. This fact also holds for different product types as every product type has different impact on, status in and relation to the customer's life. Furthermore, we discuss technically specialized filters, that means, a filter for creating recommendations for automotive products will be totally useless for TV sets.

3.1.4 Assignment of Degrees of Freedom to the Filters

Obviously not every filter has the ability to configure the whole product. On the one hand there are technical reasons. Assume a highly specialized filter for engines. For components related to the engine of a car this filter has to be applied but for all the other parts it is not feasible. Therefore, we would like to restrict the area, in which filters are able to change the product model. Additionally, there are social reasons. Again assume two customers, both related to an automotive community. Still Customers A and B are different in that Customer A appreciates the opinions about the appearance of his/her car. However, Customer B does not care for opinions about the look, though technical opinions are eagerly welcome. In conclusion, the personalization has to be executed in different ways meaning the pipeline has to be set up differently for Cus-

tomers A and B. As collaborative filters cover community aspects let us concentrate on these solely. For Customer A the collaborative filter has to influence the exterior and interior of the car while for Customer B it must concentrate on the technical parts of the product.

Furthermore we have to take the interactive character of the configuration system into account. Assume a partially restricted product model where a customer wants to get a recommendation for a certain component. Thus, it has to be possible to run the pipeline without having it touch other parts of the product model than those the customer needs a recommendation for.

3.1.5 Filter Arrangement inside the Pipeline

This parameter closely relates to the used filters in Section 3.1.3. But why is the order in which the filters are applied to the restricted product model important? Above, we just explained that each filter further restricts the product model, which is rather arbitrary. Section 3.1.4 already describes, why it is necessary to let some degrees of freedom only be configured by specific filters. Additionally, the order in which the filters are applied to the restricted product model is important for two reasons. First some degrees of freedom may be assigned to more than one filter. And as some filters relate to specific customers in a better way than others, those have to be given priority in that they have to be given precedence in operation on the product model. The other way around may allow unimportant filters to configure the product model in a way that prevents good filters to change the product model in a sensitive way, since we do not allow widening a degree of freedom currently.

Secondly, we have to deal with indirect effects from changes in the product model due to the constraint set. Even when it is prohibited that one degree of freedom can be changed by more than one filter, the order of filters in which they are applied to the product model has consequences. Constraints allow the product designer to specify dependencies in the product. Thus, though the assignment, degrees of freedom to filters may be disjunctive, constraints may eliminate that dilemma. So less important filters may configure their degrees of freedom with effects on degrees of freedom that are assigned to important filters. Surely such an indirect influence on important filters is not acceptable.

3.1.6 Special Customer Wishes

Suppose you want to buy a product and configure it interactively. Suppose the first shot based on your current customer profile information does not really correspond to your wishes, e.g., the color chosen. On the other hand, you do not want to alter all those components of the product that reference the color. Since the configuration system does not provide an sophisticated editing system allowing to change more than one degree of freedom at once and automatically, it would be great to restart the configuration system with an altered version of the customer profile. However, this can be done manually by changing the customer profile and switching back to the old version afterwards, it is less time consuming to pass the differing information directly to the filtering manager.

Another use case is to allow the customer to try different set-ups. This supports different variants of a product allowing the customer to compare visually and technically what may fit best to her/him.

3.1.7 Special Configuration Information for each Filter

Finally, filters have to be controlled with other than customer and product related data. Imagine the granularity or the relation finding of a collaborative filter. The granularity influences the number of different products used to build a new recommendation. A coarse approach is to use for all possible degrees of freedoms just the product of one relating person. A fine-grained approach would try to find different customers for different components. This is just one example for filter configuration. Each filter type may have some specific parameters.

3.2 Problems solved

In our opinion the filter combination architecture provides a solution to the goals listed in Section 2. By allowing arbitrary filters to be included in the pipeline, this architecture provides an optimal basis for making use of all customer profile information. In contrast to existing hybrids, our approach does not stipulate the type of filters used inside the pipeline. Moreover, the pipeline-based data-flow inside the pipeline as well as among the filtering modules will not depend on a specific filtering technique. Secondly, the recommendations generated are of reduced complexity, as many degrees of freedom will have been configured. The validation of the product model will be integrated into the pipeline. After each filter the restricted product model has to be validated against the constraints. Additionally, the pipeline allows the introduction of a rule-based filter that takes the product model constraints as the rule base.

3.3 Pipeline Integration into Configuration System

Figuratively, the pipeline corresponds to the working animal of the filtering manager. The filtering manager itself receives requests for personalization. It then configures the pipeline with the desired information. The methods used to configure the pipeline are partially formulated. Currently, we have some more or less clear ideas for accomplishing this task. They will be explained in Section 4 accompanied by an example. After the set-up, the pipeline will be started. The output is the restricted product model including explanations. This data will be returned to the component requesting the recommendation (from the filtering manager).

Currently, the filtering manager, especially the pipeline with its filters, is not supposed to be a self-sufficient system. It may communicate with other components of the configuration system for at least two reasons. Firstly, assume a filter detects an information hole in the customer profile. Certain data about the customer is needed to let the filter generate sensible output. We decided not to initiate a computer-customer communication directly but to inform the customer profile manager of the missing data. The recommendation process may then be aborted or finished. Afterwards or at some other stage the customer profile manager will initiate an interaction with the customer requesting more information on the desired topic.

Secondly, the component validating a restricted product model will not be included in the pipeline but in some other component at a very central point. Thus there has to be interaction between the pipeline and that validation component in order to let the recommendations be validated during personalization.

4 Example

Now we want to show the basic functionality of the pipeline. The example introduced is about a totally fictitious automobile personalization. But note, however, as this example has to show the functionality of the pipeline, we do not want to present a technically correct product model. It will be far less complex than real ones. Furthermore, its attributes, components, and constraints have been specifically chosen to help clarifying the pipeline architecture.

4.1 The Car Product Model

Figure 3 shows our simplified description (product model) of a car. Some components concentrate on technical aspects, others on the appearance and the handling. The root component, called Car, can be found on the left side. It is followed by its sub-components on the right, which again may have sub-components. Every component is underlined. There is one example for alternative components: Car.Interior.Shift Lever. This component is a placeholder for one of the alternatives. It does not have any attributes. The Car.Interior.Child Safety Seat is optional, of course.

All attributes are printed below their components. They are specified by name and domain. For instance, the `power` of the engine has a linear domain ranging from 30 to 90. Every value may be specified. On the other hand, the gear count only provides a choice of three different numbers. This is a so-called enumerated attribute. Another enumerated attribute for example is Car.Interior.Seat cover. It lets the customer choose between three textually represented values of a controlled vocabulary. In order to specify the lacquer color more easily, we just use an RGB-scheme. Of course this may be different in a real-world product model.

Figure 3: Product Model Example for a Car

Having described the shell, which provides information about the patronymic structure and its degrees of freedom, we still need to say something about internal dependencies. Therefore our (fictitious) constraints are:

$$(1) \text{Car.Engine.Cylinder Capacity} * \text{Car.Engine.Cylinder} / 2.22 = (\text{Car.Engine.Power})^2$$

$$(2) \text{Car.Engine.Power} > 50 \text{ kWh} \Rightarrow \text{Car.Gears.Count} \geq 5$$

(3) Car.Gears.Type = "manual" ⇔
Car.Interior.Shift Lever is Car.Interior.Manual Gears Lever

(4) Car.Interior.Seat cover = "leather" ⇒
Car.Interior.Child Safety Seat.Color = "brown"

Component and attribute names are printed in courier font. Names of hierarchically organized components are separated by dots. In addition to that, components will be underlined in the same way like in the product model.

Well, what do the constraints express? We will give semi-technical comments on their plausibility. Constraint (1) takes care of technical dependencies inside the engine. Obviously, requesting an engine with high power but low number of cylinders and cylinder capacity will not work. The second constraint (2) has been introduced to allow the customer to treat engines with high power with care. Therefore, a higher number of gears will be enforced for powerful and, hence, fast cars. The next constraint (3) reflects the necessity to integrate the correct handles. In case the customer selects manual gears the handles have to be adjusted in the same way. Finally, constraint (4) realizes aesthetic requirements. In case the customer selects high quality clothing for the seats (here: "leather") the child safety seat has to be adjusted in its color so that the look is not disturbed. Actually, this constraint may be formulated less strictly. Currently, leather in the interior enforces a brown safety seat. By using default values in the product model the constraint can be changed in a way that it sets the default value rather than restricting the domain of the color. In this case the customer would still have the opportunity to select a different color for the seat.

As you can see, constraints not always concentrate on attributes of a certain component. Dependencies touching different components are necessary, e.g., (3). Actually very few constraints have been formulated. In combination with a more elaborated product one can image a vast number of other possible other constraints.

With the product model introduced, the point is reached where a customer may consult the system to buy a new product. The product model information introduced so far is the only data the configuration system gets. It will be created by the product designer and contains all information about the product that is necessary to configure tailored variants.

4.2 The Customer

Now an example customer profile has to be set up. The profile will contain all the necessary information to configure the pipeline and more or less build a recommendation for the customer. In real-world product personalization, the customer profile may be less optimal. For example, important information may be missing. In that case the recommendation will look differently and less tailored to the customer's needs. However, this paper does not concentrate on techniques for acquiring meaningful customer data and identity management. Section 1.2 gives pointers to the literature in the field of customer profiling.

Our customer, let us call him Pete, is no technical expert and therefore does not have any deep knowledge to personally configure his car. Nor does his customer profile contain much technical information about wishes and requirements for future car set-ups. Pete is married and father of two children, two and eight years old (all mined in the cus-

tomer profile at common places). Despite his lack in technical knowledge, Pete has a few friends living in the same social environment who already bought a car via the virtual store. Thus, this information has been stored in the database and is accessible while Pete configures his new car. Security issues have to be dealt with, too. However, we assume the friends agreed to let Pete's recommender system access their car product configurations. The configuration system knows about the deep relation to his friends. Pete's previous cars have been bought via the same system. Their configuration is still stored in the database.

4.3 The Recommendation Process

Pete comes into the virtual store to tailor his new car. After starting the configuration system he orders the system to create a recommendation for him. This activity triggers the filtering manager, which is responsible for creating recommendations. It will be passed the customer identification and a yet unrestricted product model as shown in Figure 3. The filtering manager now sets up the pipeline. Therefore, the seven configuration parameters explained in Section 3.1 have to be calculated.

4.3.1 Pipeline Configuration

The *customer* addressing the filtering manager is Pete. This is the key to access his customer profile. It has been passed to the filtering manager already and therefore needs no further calculation. It will be used throughout the whole recommendation process.

The same holds for the (*restricted*) *initial product model*. The filtering manager gets this structure from the configuration system. For new products this is just a copy of the original product model.

The first less easy configurable parameter is the *set of filters* used inside the pipeline. In real configuration systems there may be hundreds of different filters. First think of all the product specific filters. Additionally, there are collaborative filters working with different granularities. With respect to the size of the entities they decompose the product model into in order to generate recommendations for each of those entities separately. Furthermore, those collaborative filters use different algorithms to detect communities and links between customers. And, finally, there are other filters like content-based and rule-based filters. So it is no easy task to select the correct filter! The solutions range from totally manual, where the customer does this selection on his own, to fully automatic, where the system does the work. Semi-automatic solutions are template sets of filters assembled by the product designer. One possible solution for selecting the used filters automatically is to categorize them first and then use one filter from each category. Categories can be "collaborative", "content-based", "product related", etc. Still there is the problem of selecting the right filter of a specific category. This problem may be dealt with via analysing the richness of available customer information needed for that specific filter.

In this example we will manually select the filters. Since the system knows about relating customers a collaborative filter has to be used for sure. In addition to the relating customers, there is some knowledge of the social environment in the customer profile. Either a rule-based (maybe product specific) or an arbitrary product specific filter is feasible. Therefore, let us select both of them. After all, the following filters will be used: collaborative, car-specific, and rule-based.

Closely related to the previous parameter is the question of the *filter arrangement* inside the pipeline. Again, the solution for assessing a configuration for this one ranges from manual to automatic. To let the customer specify the order imposes more work to him on the one hand. This is bad because he may not know anything about filtering and the related techniques. On the other hand, he will be able to play around a little bit and find an optimal solution for himself. For novice customers or customers, who do not want to deal with such things, there may be templates of filter arrangements, possibly using the filter categories introduced above. Those categories can be placeholders in the arrangement templates and will be substituted by the actual filters used. Another solution is to look for previous purchases of such products. Because people normally do not change interests rapidly, the concern for a specific product will stay the same over years and therefore the private knowledge in those fields, too. Thus, previous arrangements of filters in the pipeline may work with the same efficiency. Actually, this technique can also be used for determining the previous parameter (used filters).

In this example, let us assume there is a common template for arranging the filters. First it is most feasible to use the car-specific as this closely knows the product structure and handles best personal information. The second filter should be the collaborative one. Due to Pete's social environment it is very likely that the friends own cars with optimal values for people living in the same environment. Last but not least, the rule-based filter will be used.

The most tedious and difficult configuration parameter for the pipeline is the *assignment of the attributes to the filters*. This assignment can be specified very precisely on the level of attributes. On a less detailed level whole components can be assigned to specific filters. Therefore, forcing the customer to manually give the attribute-filter assignments is not a good idea. He will be totally overwhelmed and, in addition to that, a big amount of technical knowledge is necessary. Afresh, an at least semi-automatic method is needed. The product designer may decide which component or attribute mostly gets configured best by which filter (category). Every component/attribute then needs to get annotated with such information. The filtering manager uses this information to find out which filter has to be used. Remember, the assignment of an attribute to a filter does not mean that the filter is forced to restrict this attribute. It can be left untouched. And, as planned in our approach, the same attribute may be assigned to more than one filter.

For Pete, let us assume the following assignment that tries to reflect the fact that certain filters are suited for specific parts of the product best due to the content of his customer profile.

1. Collaborative: Car.Exterior, Car.Engine
2. Rule-based: Car.Interior (except Child Safety Seat)
3. Car specific: Car.Gears, Car.Interior.Child Safety Seat

Customer wishes will not be used in our example. However, the configuration system has to pass this information to the filtering manager anyway. Currently, its structure will be the same as the one of the customer profile. The attributes in the customer wishes will override those of the profile. In case the customer wishes do not contain certain information, the information from the profile will be selected—if present. Just think of a transparent double-layered customer profile.

In contrast to the previous parameter, the *additional configuration for specific filters* is not customer-dependent. In our case, we want the collaborative filter not to work very detailed. So it will not try to decompose its assigned attributes and separately personalize each of them. The product-specific filter is not configurable anyway. A closer look should be given to the rule-based filter. Here we still have to look for a rule base. This rule base is either customer-specific or generic. Since Pete does not have any deep knowledge of cars, his profile most might not contain any rules. Assume there is a generic rule base created by a product designer or expert customer. Rules of interest are:

1. In case the customer profile contains a lot of sportive activities, the steering wheel size will be reduced to 35 cm. This rule assumes that customers with high interest in sports prefer a sportive layout of the interior of the car.
2. The second rule takes the yearly income into account. In case this is greater than a certain threshold, the seat cover will be set to leather, which is pretty expensive. Otherwise, leather will be removed from the options.
3. Another rule specifies whether to enable the child safety seat option if there is a child with an age less than six years in the family.

Many rules can be thought of. Of course, the car-specific filter may have this logic integrated, too. But even product-specific filters are not perfect and generic rule-based filters allow customers to further optimize the configuration process. The rules may be organized by the community of interest themselves. This will give communities the power to create their own configuration scheme besides the already explained collaborative filter. In our example, we do not organize the rules. Just those rules mentioned are of interest in this example.

It is obvious, that many of the configuration parameters for the pipeline are somehow interconnected. For instance, the available rules for a rule-based filter affect the attributes that filter is able to configure. Therefore, those attributes should be assigned to the rule-based filter and no others. Still many techniques can be thought of to configure the pipeline. This actually very simple example already shows the power and difficulties of our approach.

4.3.2 Pipeline in Action

With this extensive configuration, the pipeline can be activated. As the pipeline itself just acts as a container and information flow facilitator, no further configuration will be done inside. The pipeline itself uses the arrangement of the filters and activates them subsequently. The example will be presented filter by filter, each time interrupted by a validation step. After each filter and each validation step, the newly restricted product model will be illustrated. The convention for those figures is the following. Values removed by the filters will be removed in the figure. Values and components removed by the validation phase will be crossed out first and then removed in the following figure.

In Pete's case, the first filter is the car-specific filter. As specified in Section 4.3.1, the car specific-filter is responsible for personalizing gears and the child safety seat. This filter contains hard-wired logic and basically works on the customer profile. There it uses standard attributes in order to transfer them meaningfully restricting the product model. Those attributes are standardized by the customer profile component. They will not be introduced here. First let us focus on the child safety seat component, and

whether this has to be included into the product model. The customer profile contains information about family status and children. Since Pete is father of a very young child (encoded in specific attributes of the profile), the filter decides to include the child safety seat. The color will be left untouched, though potentially the child's customer profile can be examined for his/her favourite color. However, this action would need such a profile to be present which is not very likely at that age. Furthermore, the father has to provide an access key in order to access his child's profile.

Further, the gears have to be configured. In this case, the car-specific filter uses old car configurations of Pete. Previously bought cars may give hints. In this case, Pete already bought a car with manual gears. Thus the gears will be set to "manual". Another approach may be imaginable. In every country, people have a certain preference for the shifts. Using the home country from the customer profile allows the filter to draw conclusions for the type of gears. As the count of gears is related to the technical set-up this attribute will be left untouched.

Now the first filter is finished and hands the restricted product model back to the pipeline. The required validation step will be started automatically. The validator is responsible for enforcing the constraints on the product model. Constraints (1), (2), and (4) still hold. However, constraint (3) is not satisfied anymore. The gears have been set to manual without restricting the alternatives for the shift lever. Thus the validator automatically sets the alternative so that the constraint is satisfied again. In this case the Manual Gears Lever has to be chosen. The final restricted product model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Restricted Product Model after Car specific Filter & Validation

The second filter applied on the restricted product model shown in Figure 4 is the collaborative filter. This filter works in the following way. Firstly, it gathers the related people. Since the filter specific configuration does not contain any community information the filter uses the customer profile to determine the friends. The profile contains the connections to other people augmented by a value showing how good that relation is. Since there have been large research efforts in community detection, we will not dive into this. A very simple approach will be used here. The community is built with all the people who have a very well rated relation to Pete, e.g., a value greater than 0.8 on a scale from -1 to 1. Now the filter retrieves all previous car purchases of the members of the community. That search will result in a simple set of product configurations. The collaborative filter then restricts its attributes to the values of those product configurations. Obviously, this is very easy and it is needless to go into more depth. Figure 5

presents the resulting restricted product model. The color and all attributes of the engine have been narrowed.

Remember, the validation phase still has to be passed. In this case, the engine has been configured so that constraint (1) is still fulfilled with certain combinations of the values. In other cases, this part had to be marked invalid. Just rejecting the configuration would not help since the customer would not be able to get any recommendation. However, one more constraint has to be paid attention to. (2) will lead to a restriction of the gear count due to a narrowed range of values for the power attribute. The value “4” will be removed, and that’s the reason for this number being crossed out in Figure 5. No other changes to the restricted product model are necessary. The result is input to the last filter.

Figure 5: Restricted Product Model after the Collaborative Filter & Validation

Finally the rule-based filter will receive the model shown in Figure 5. It configures the interior except the child safety seat.

In Section 4.3.1, three rules have been introduced. The first rule triggers the rule-based filter to look for Pete’s sport activities. Of course, the appropriate attributes holding this information in the customer profile have to be specified in the rule. Unfortunately, the rule-based filter does not find many activities and thus leaves the steering wheel size untouched.

For rule number two, the yearly income in the customer profile is needed. Pete’s is pretty high, which leads the filter to set the seat cover attribute to “leather”.

The third rule will be triggered, too, but the child safety seat and its attributes are out of reach for the rule-based filter due to the attribute to filter assignment. So the last rule will be ignored. Last but not least, the validation phase needs to be passed. Attributes of the constraints (1), (2), and (3) did not change and thus those constraints still hold. However, the last constraint (4) causes the color of the child safety seat to be set to “brown”.

Figure 6 shows the result. It will be returned to the configuration system and presented to the customer.

Figure 6: Restricted Product Model after the Rule-based Filter & Validation

4.4 Final Remarks

In comparison the product model shown in Figure 6 is much more concise than the one in Figure 3. Still the customer has to further configure the product but the range of values has been restricted extremely. Basically, it is a choice between a more powerful or less powerful car. Some attention has to be paid to the color and the gear count. Since the product model also contains default values, customer action may not even be needed anymore. Default values of attributes have not been introduced in this example to keep it simple enough. If used the filters may alter those values. Of course, each default value has to be in the (restricted) range of its attribute. After all, the recommendation process has helped Pete to find a suitable car for his family. It fits into his social environment and basically fulfils his needs.

The example showed the complexity of the pipeline and its configuration. For standard customers it does not seem feasible to let them do any of the configuration of the pipeline. At least semi-automatic solutions like configuration templates for the parameters of the pipeline have to be provided. Also, the interconnection between different parameters has been shown: The car specific filter contained logics that had been integrated into the rules for the rule-based filter, too. One cannot avoid this. Thus there will never be an optimal pipeline set-up since too many factors will influence the efficiency.

The recommendation process will get even more complex when adding features left out in this example:

- Let filters trigger the customer profile to query the customer on missing personal information.
- Allow overlapping assignment from attributes to filters.
- Introduce qualities for products. Qualities are value templates for a certain number of attributes. The product designer specifies them.
- Add explanations why attributes have been configured that way.

5 Conclusion & Future Work

In this paper we explicitly presented a way to generate recommendations in a product configuration system. We showed that current approaches are inadequate and introduced a pipelined combination of arbitrary personalization modules. The basic function of that pipeline has been explained with a detailed introduction to the parameters configuring the pipeline. With an extended example, we tried to clarify the personalization procedure realized by our approach. This example showed the feasibility of our approach, though it has been made clear that optimally configuring the pipeline is a very difficult task.

Still the flexibility of the architecture allows arbitrary filters to be introduced, even in the future. Thus we are not bound to current techniques. However, the simple one-filter scenario is possible, too, since the pipelined can be configured in this way.

In the future, research has to be invested especially in the area of pipeline configuration. More semi-automatic and automatic solutions must be introduced for selecting and arranging the filters and for assigning attributes to them. Furthermore, the pipeline itself has to be enhanced. Currently, a simple sequence of filters is allowed. In the future, loops may be realized to find fix-points in recommendations. Because of the necessary validation phase, we also need complex validation techniques allowing intelligent application of the constraints. Rejecting a restricted product model in early stages will lead to frustrated customers.

6 References

Balabanović, Shoham (1997): FAB: Content-Based, Collaborative Recommendation, *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 40, No. 3, pp. 66 – 72, March 1997

Basu, Hirsh, Cohen (1998): Recommendation as classification: Using social and Content-based Information in Recommendation, in: *Proceedings of the 15th national/10th Conference on Artificial Intelligence/Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AAAI/IAAI 1998)*. Menlo Park, USA: American Association for Artificial Intelligence

Koch (2002): Globale Benutzerprofile und kundenindividuelle Produkte, in: *Proceedings of the 4th Wirtschaftsinformatik-Symposium*, Vaduz, Liechtenstein, June 2002, Teubner-Verlag

Koch, Möslin (2003): User Representation in E-Commerce and Collaboration Applications, in: *Proceedings of the 16th Bled Electronic Commerce Conference eTransformation*, Bled, Slovenia, June 9-11, 2003

Koch, Schubert (2002): Personalization and Community Communication for Customer Support, in: *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Work With Display Units – World Wide Work (WWDU 2002)*, Bertechsgaden, Germany, May 2002

Leckner, Koch, Stegmann, Lacher (2003): Personalization Meets Mass Customization, Support for the Configuration and Design of Individualized Products, in: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems (ICEIS 2003)*, Paris, April 2003

Leckner, Lacher (2003): Simplifying Configuration through Customer oriented Product Models, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Engineering Design (ICED 03), Stockholm, August 19-21, 2003

Meteren, Someren (2000): Using Content-Based Filtering for Recommendation, in: Proceedings of ECML 2000 Workshop: Machine Learning in New Information Age, Barcelona, Spain, 2000, pp. 47-56

Renneberg, Borghoff (2003): Pipelined Filter Combination in Product Personalization, in: Stephanidis, C. (ed.): Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (HCI 2003), Crete, Greece, June 22-27, 2003. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Ass. Publ., Vol. 4, pp. 602-606

Resnick, Varian (1997): Recommender Systems, Communications of the ACM, Vol. 40, No. 3, pp. 56 – 58, March 1997

Sarwar, Karypis, Konstan, Riedl (2001): Item-Based Collaborative Filtering Recommendation Algorithms, in: Proceedings of the 10th International World Wide Web Conference (WWW10), Hong Kong, May 2001

Schein, Popescul, Ungar, Pennock (2002): Methods and Metrics for Cold-Start Recommendations, in: Proceedings of the 25th Annual International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, 2002 NY, USA: ACM Press, pp. 253-260

Soboroff, Nicholas (2002): Related, but not Relevant: Content-Based Collaborative Filtering in TREC-8. Information Retrieval **5**:2-3, pp. 189-208

Stegmann, Koch, Lacher, Leckner, Renneberg (2003): Generating Personalized Recommendations in a Model-Based Product Configurator System, in: Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI 2003) (accepted, to appear)